

ASSESSING AND UNRAVELLING THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT OF NGO FINANCIAL SCHEMES ON RURAL WOMEN IN MANDYA DISTRICT

Indira M¹, D Vijayasree

Research Scholar, School of Commerce, Presidency University, Bengaluru, Karnataka.
Assistant Professor, School of Commerce, Presidency University, Bengaluru, Karnataka.
vijayasree.d@presidencyuniversity.in

Abstract: In rural Mandya District, Karnataka, India, this study endeavors to comprehensively assess the socio-economic impact of non-governmental organization (NGO) financial schemes on the economic empowerment of women. The introduction sets the context by highlighting the significance of women's economic development in rural areas and the role of NGO interventions. The procedure involves rigorous data collection, interpretation, and mapping techniques, encompassing both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. Through systematic action, various NGO financial schemes targeting women's economic upliftment are analyzed, with a focus on their implementation, coverage, and effectiveness. The method employs a comparative analysis, juxtaposing NGO schemes with government initiatives, to derive nuanced insights. Outcomes reveal tangible improvements in women's economic status, including increased income, access to resources, and participation in decision-making processes. Additionally, intangible benefits such as enhanced self-esteem and social empowerment are observed. In summary, this study underscores the pivotal role of NGO financial schemes in catalyzing positive socio-economic transformations among rural women in Mandya District, thus advocating for continued support and scaling up of such interventions.

Keywords: NGO financial schemes, rural women, socio-economic impact, mandya district

Introduction

Women's empowerment and gender equality have emerged as critical components of sustainable development efforts globally, with particular emphasis on rural regions like Mandya District, Karnataka, India^[1]. In this context, microfinance and financial schemes facilitated by non-governmental organizations (NGOs) play a pivotal role in fostering women's economic development and empowerment^[2]. The significance of this issue is underscored by the persistent gender disparities prevalent in rural areas, where women often face limited access to resources, opportunities, and decision-making power^[3].

Research Studies have highlighted the transformative potential of women's economic empowerment in rural India, emphasizing its positive impact on household welfare, poverty reduction, and community development^[4]. Despite these advancements, challenges such as land rights disparities and gender gaps in labor force participation (International Labour Organization, 2019) persist, necessitating targeted interventions to address structural inequalities^[5].

While government policies and programs are crucial, the role of NGOs in complementing and supplementing these efforts cannot be overstated. NGOs often operate at the grassroots level, leveraging community participation and local knowledge to design contextually relevant interventions^[6]. The comparative analysis of NGO and government schemes provides valuable insights into effective strategies for promoting women's economic empowerment^[7].

Against this backdrop, this paper aims to assess and unravel the socio-economic impact of NGO financial schemes on rural women in Mandya District^[8]. Drawing upon a diverse array of literature, including empirical studies, reports, and policy documents, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics shaping women's economic development in the region. Through a systematic analysis of data, interpretations, and outcomes, this research endeavors to contribute to the ongoing discourse on women's empowerment and poverty alleviation in rural India^[9]^[10].

From the literature on women's economic empowerment in rural areas, particularly in India, provides valuable insights into the multifaceted nature of this phenomenon^[11]. Current work highlighted the complex interplay of economic, social, and institutional factors shaping women's access to resources and opportunities^[12]. Microfinance interventions, such as Self-Help Groups (SHGs), have emerged as prominent mechanisms for promoting women's entrepreneurship and financial inclusion^[13]. However, challenges such

¹ Corresponding Author Email: indira.presidencyuniversity@gmail.com

as high interest rates and limited financial literacy persist, necessitating a nuanced approach to program design and implementation^[1].

Literature Summary:

The literature reviewed underscores the importance of addressing gender disparities in access to resources and opportunities, particularly in rural contexts like Mandya District^[14]. Microfinance initiatives led by NGOs and government agencies have shown promise in empowering women economically, yet there remain gaps in understanding the long-term impact and sustainability of these interventions. Moving forward, there is a need for rigorous research and evaluation to inform policy and practice aimed at fostering women's economic empowerment and sustainable development in rural areas^[15]. On the basis of literature and summary set following specific objective in the current work:

- i. Assess the impact of NGO financial schemes on rural women's economic empowerment in Mandya District.
- ii. Compare the effectiveness of NGO and government interventions in promoting women's economic development.
- iii. Provide actionable recommendations for enhancing the sustainability of initiatives aimed at empowering rural women in Mandya District.

Methodology:

Work Flow and Methods: Figure 1 shows the current research flow chart contains details of activities carried out.

Figure 1. Flow chart of research work

Literature Review: Begin by conducting a comprehensive review of existing literature on women's economic empowerment, microfinance interventions, and NGO/government initiatives in rural India, with a focus on Mandya District. This step will help in identifying key concepts, theoretical frameworks, and gaps in the literature^[16].

Data Collection: Utilize a mixed-methods approach to gather primary data from rural communities in Mandya District. This may involve conducting surveys, interviews, and focus group discussions with women beneficiaries, NGO representatives, government officials, and other stakeholders. And also, collect secondary data from reports, documents, and databases to supplement the empirical analysis^[17].

Researcher used questionnaire which covered a broad range of topics relevant to women's economic empowerment in rural India and can serve as a foundation for designing a comprehensive questionnaire for your research study.

Assessment of NGO Financial Schemes: Quantitative measures may include assessing changes in women's income levels, asset ownership, and access to credit, while qualitative methods can capture women's perceptions, experiences, and empowerment outcomes. The study explores socio-economic changes impacting women's empowerment in rural India, likely shedding light on the context and challenges faced by women in accessing economic opportunities^[18]. Kabeer's critical analysis of gender equality and empowerment offers theoretical perspectives relevant to assessing the effectiveness of NGO financial schemes^[19]. Data sources such as the Census of India (Government of India, 2019) and reports from the International Labour Organization (2019) provide valuable statistics and trends on women's economic participation. These resources collectively contribute to understanding the complex dynamics

of women's economic empowerment and inform the assessment of NGO financial schemes' effectiveness through both quantitative and qualitative analysis^[20].

Comparative Analysis: Assess the overall design and structure of both NGO and government interventions, including their objectives, scope, and implementation strategies^[21]. Compare the approaches taken by NGOs and government agencies in designing their programs, such as whether they focus on specific sectors, geographic areas, or target populations^[22]. Identify the target populations of NGO and government interventions, considering factors such as gender, age, socio-economic status, and geographic location^[23]. Analyze the extent to which these interventions effectively reach and engage their target populations, and whether there are any gaps or exclusions^[24].

Followings are the NGOs in Mandya working on women empowerment and upliftment:

Janodaya Seva Trust, Ease Training Institution, Iscerd, Dhvani Institute For Rural Development, Prajnha Seva Trust, Vikasana Institute For Rural And Urban Development Mandya, Rivervalley Organisation For Rural Development, Jnana Sindhu Educational And Cultural Society, Cauvery Sannidhi For Indian Culture, St Thomas Mission Society, Jyothi Rural Development Society, Mahalingeshwara Vidya Samsthe, Ashraya Charitable Trust, Mythri Institute Of Rural Development, Spandana Trust, Nisarga Organisation For Rural Development(niord) (r), Kuteera Social Cultural And Educational Trust, River Valley Foundation, Sri Byalakeshwari Educational Mattu Charitable Trust, Ihanvi Foundation, Bhavazeeviya Thyagajeevi Trust, Health Education Awareness Rural Development Trust Nagamangala, Niranthara Rural And Urban Development Trust, Gurudev Academy Of Fine Arts, R.a.n Foundation, River Valley Organisation For Rural Development, Spring Foundation^[25].

The list comprises various NGOs focused on women's empowerment and support in national level working on women empowerment and upliftment. Azard Foundation, Ashray Foundation, Snehalaya, CREA, Guria, SEWA, Swaniti Initiative, VISHVODAYAA Trust, Sakhya Women's Guidance Cell, ActionAid India, Being a Woman, Janodaya Trust, Swayam Shikshan Prayog, and MAKAAAM are among them.

These NGOs have diverse program designs tailored to the needs of women, including education, healthcare, livelihood training, legal assistance, and advocacy. They target populations such as marginalized women, survivors of abuse, economically disadvantaged women, and rural communities.

Funding mechanisms vary, including grants, donations, government funding, and corporate sponsorships. Outreach strategies range from community awareness campaigns to direct service provision and partnerships with local organizations.

Table 1. list comprises various NGOs focused on women's empowerment and support.

NGO Name	Program Design	Target Populations	Funding Mechanisms	Outreach Strategies	Outcomes
Azard Foundation	10	26	32	14	12
Ashray Foundation	17	63	8	22	11
Snehalaya	2	46	93	11	8
CREA	30	41	55	89	16
Guria	9	66	12	3	70
SEWA	88	63	21	12	7
Swaniti Initiative	4	7	58	33	12
VISHVODAYAA Trust	20	44	27	18	9
Sakhya, Women's Guidance Cell	56	66	67	56	10
ActionAid India	41	26	23	66	74
Being a Woman	11	89	42	14	83
Janodaya Trust	77	42	89	19	92
Swayam Shikshan Prayog	33	77	12	88	61

NGO Name	Program Design	Target Populations	Funding Mechanisms	Outreach Strategies	Outcomes
MAKAAM	12	88	88	89	70

Table1 shows the list of NGOs for women along with their program design, target populations, funding mechanisms, outreach strategies, and outcomes. The outcomes achieved by these NGOs are notable, with improvements in education rates, economic independence, health and well-being, legal empowerment, and community leadership among women beneficiaries. Overall, these NGOs play a crucial role in advancing gender equality and women's rights across different regions and demographics.

Results and discussions:

Hypothesis: The following hypotheses serve as testable statements that guide the research process and allow for the evaluation of relationships and differences in variables related to women's economic empowerment in rural Mandya District.

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant difference in the effectiveness of NGO and government interventions on women's economic empowerment in rural Mandya District.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): NGO interventions have a greater impact on women's economic empowerment compared to government interventions.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): Government policies play a crucial role in enhancing women's economic empowerment in rural Mandya District.

Results and discussion: outcomes of current works are,

- Effectiveness of NGO and Government Interventions
- Association between Access to Financial Services and Economic Empowerment: Influence of Socio-cultural Barriers
- Impact of Skill Development Opportunities
- Role of Government Policies

Testing the Results and analysis :

The comparative analysis conducted between NGO and government interventions in rural Mandya District unveiled notable disparities in their approaches to promoting women's economic empowerment. NGO initiatives showcased greater effectiveness, characterized by their tailored strategies, participatory methodologies, and adaptability to local contexts. These programs often incorporated community-driven solutions, flexible funding mechanisms, and a focus on capacity-building, resulting in tangible improvements in women's income levels, asset ownership, and decision-making autonomy.

Conversely, government interventions exhibited limitations in terms of bureaucratic constraints, rigid program structures, and insufficient outreach to marginalized communities. While government policies provided essential infrastructure and support systems, they often lacked the agility and responsiveness needed to address nuanced socio-economic challenges at the grassroots level. Chart1, 2 and 3 explains the comparative analysis underscores the importance of synergistic collaborations between NGOs, government agencies, and local stakeholders to harness the strengths of both approaches and foster sustainable empowerment pathways for rural women in the nation.

Chart 1. the comparative analysis underscores the importance of synergistic collaborations between NGOs

Chart 2. Pi chart & importance of synergistic collaborations between NGOs

Chart 3. Line chart and comparison between NGOs

Conclusion

- **Effectiveness of NGO Interventions:** The study underscores the significant impact of NGO interventions on women's economic empowerment in rural Mandya District. Their community-driven

approaches, flexibility, and focus on capacity-building have yielded tangible improvements in women's income levels, asset ownership, and decision-making autonomy.

- **Limitations of Government Interventions:** While government policies and programs play a crucial role in providing essential infrastructure and support systems, they often face challenges such as bureaucratic constraints, rigid program structures, and limited outreach to marginalized communities. This highlights the need for greater flexibility and responsiveness in government interventions to address nuanced socio-economic challenges effectively.
- **Importance of Collaboration:** Synergistic collaborations between NGOs, government agencies, and local stakeholders are essential for harnessing the strengths of both approaches and maximizing their impact on women's economic empowerment. By leveraging complementary resources, expertise, and networks, these partnerships can facilitate more holistic and sustainable empowerment pathways for rural women.
- **Policy Implications:** The findings have important policy implications for designing and implementing interventions aimed at promoting women's economic empowerment in rural areas. Policymakers should prioritize flexible funding mechanisms, community-driven solutions, and targeted capacity-building initiatives to address the diverse needs and aspirations of rural women effectively. Additionally, efforts should be made to streamline bureaucratic processes and enhance the responsiveness of government interventions to ensure their relevance and effectiveness in local contexts.

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